

Critical Thinking Skills for Primary Education: Teachers' Perceptions

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Abstract

In light of interest in the process of educational development, primary education level outputs, and achieving strategic learning objectives, the study at hand aimed to identify critical thinking skills according to primary education teachers' perceptions. This was done by determining teacher knowledge regarding critical thinking skills and the importance of the aforementioned in curriculum, from the viewpoint of primary school teachers. The study also sought to determine any effect that qualifications and experience might have on teacher perceptions towards equipping students with critical thinking skills.

The study's population was limited to obtaining female teachers' perceptions of critical thinking skills for primary education. A total of 385 female teachers who taught in the public primary schools affiliated to the Diriyah office in the region of Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, during the academic year 2021, were invited to complete and return the survey. Eventually, 197 completed the survey and submitted their responses. The study found a high level of knowledge of critical thinking skills and a high agreement on the importance of including critical thinking skills in the primary school curriculum and the importance of providing primary school students with critical thinking skills. The study concluded that there was no impact of the qualifications and experience variables on the primary school teachers' points of view regarding the importance of including critical thinking skills in the curriculum and the importance of students' acquisition of those skills.

Introduction

Given the myriad of changes in the twenty-first century, many aspire to achieve technological development and continuous scientific progress. This gives attention to educational institutions and the employment of modern programs and strategies in education, as critical thinking skills make the learners effective individuals capable of solving problems. The importance of critical thinking skills crystallizes in not being limited to decision-making or solving the problem, but it goes beyond that towards the ability to analyze and inspire innovation (Asari, 2014).

Critical thinking skills are mainly related to the students' ability to explain, which begins with defining an idea and realizing its logical reasons. This is followed by thinking deeply about whether it is acceptable and thus developing the student's ability to judge evidence, which is an entry point for acquiring ample knowledge in the early stages. Developing critical thinking in childhood to achieve the goals of contemporary education is of great importance (UNESCO, 2013). The childhood stage or the stage of basic education is an ideal stage for learning skills and laying the initial foundations for achieving growth and creating the motivation to practice those skills in the future. Rather, it should be considered an urgent necessity and a basic need such as learning to read, write, think, and acquire life skills as well as make necessary decisions (Lee, 2018).

Critical thinking skills consist of knowledge, a set of mental skills, observation, discrimination, comparison, interpretation, and analysis skills, thus helping the thinker to formulate, organize and evaluate information. Some researchers even indicate that critical thinking includes elements of values, emotions, subjective judgments, perseverance, and accuracy (Al-Zou'bi, 2021).

Davies (2013) said that the educational development movement in the basic education stage, led to the use of critical and creative thinking skills in classifying and analyzing information to reach conclusions. Additionally, other outcomes comprise proposing and evaluating various solutions to problems, and planning to carry out research and investigations based on the values of instilling skills to achieve the goals of education development.

The development of critical thinking skills is certainly related to the level of teaching methods used by the teacher, the ability to see the inputs of the educational process, the skill in guidance, and the quality of the individual's previous experiences. Given what is known of learning and acquiring skills as a reality, it was important to design the curriculum in a way that allows for the development of creativity, helps to release students' ideas and stimulates their motivation towards innovation and creativity based on scientific foundation which provide an opportunity for studied logical ideas (McLaren, 2015).

There is a special requirement for students to acquire critical thinking skills in relation to cognitive theory, which is concerned with interpreting and analyzing behavior by focusing on thinking from a cognitive mental perspective, whereby a person learns to think and perceive situations from realizing previous knowledge (Muertigue&Naiker, 2022). (Winartiet al., 2019). The relationship between critical thinking skills and creative thinking skills enables the learner to acquire other skills, especially in an era which witnessed the explosion of knowledge. The aforementioned also provides a means to develop these skills in students, including the strategy of multiple intelligences referred to by (Sariet al., 2019). Similarly, there is also the effectiveness in developing critical and innovative thinking, in addition to cognitive operations programs, metacognitive programs, language and symbolic processing programs, discovery learning programs, and systematic thinking education programs. All of these programs work on developing the capabilities, abilities and skills of the student, all of which depend on improving the teacher's skills in all aspects of cognitiveskill. The development of critical thinking skills has become an educational necessity to protect the minds of learners, and the teacher can develop them through two tracks, the school curriculum path, or the path of teaching critical thinking outside the curriculum (Ansarin&Khatibi, 2018).

From the above-mentioned, we see the importance of exposure to the teacher's perceptions towards roles and practices in developing critical thinking skills, especially for the primary stage.

Statement of the Problem:

Teachers have an important key role in promoting critical thinking. The teacher is one of the two sides of the educational process (teacher and students), which focuses on achieving the desired results of education in the age of knowledge, as well as the aspirations and requirements of society. From this point of view, the teacher is the means to achieve the objectives of the curriculum, including the experiences it contains, that refine the skills of students (Jenkins&Andenoro, 2016). Accordingly, the primary stage is perhaps the most vital learning stage. The society, the achievement of educational renaissance and excellence, and the beginning of the formation of one's personal and self-skills, which include the middle and late childhood stages, pave the way for the scientific and intellectual level in the minds of students, which will have an impact on the future of these learners (PANGANORON-JABONETE, 2022). Many researchers have emphasized the importance of developing critical thinking skills among students starting at the primary stages of education (Sarwantoet al., 2021). In doing so, critical thinking skills are linked with metacognitive thinking skills and this affects students' behavior and interactions with society. Likewise, it also develops their innovative abilities. (Mohammed, 2019), (Kurniatiet al., 2022) and(Amin&Adiansyah, 2018) pay special attention to the issue of developing critical thinking skills at an early age due to the need to provide children with the ability to make judgments on ideas and perceptions and help in the process of building knowledge.

The study of Rosbaet al.(2021) also focused on the role of the teacher in developing critical thinking skills based on their importance, effectiveness, and the role in providing students with twenty-first century skills. These were included in the study of Plummer et al. (2022) in the context of the distinguished and guiding role of the teacher in developing these skills. Given the sensitivity and importance of the teacher's implementation of her role at the primary stage, the main question of the study can be determined as follows: **What are the teacher's perceptions of developing critical thinking skills for primary stage students?**

Research Questions

- 1 -What is the degree of knowledge of primary school teachers about critical thinking skills?
- 2 -What is the importance of including critical thinking skills in curriculum from the point of view of primary school teachers?
- 3 -Are there statistically significant differences in the viewpoint of primary school teachers towards students' acquisition of critical thinking skills due to the variable of qualifications?
- 4 -Are there statistically significant differences in the viewpoint of primary school teachers towards students' acquisition of critical thinking skills due to the variable of experience?

Objectives of the Study:

- 1 -Determining the degree of knowledge of primary school teachers about critical thinking skills and its skills.
- 2 -Analyzing the importance of including critical thinking skills in curriculum from the point of view of primary school teachers.
- 3-Finding out whether there is an effect of the variables of qualificationsand experience from the point of view of primary school teachers towards providing students with critical thinking skills.

Significance of the Study:

Thinking is a wide-ranging mental activity that requires acquiring knowledge. Additionally, processing the acquired produces more of it and therefore depends on multiple mental and cognitive processes closely related to the role and objectives of education and the teacher at the basic education stage. The significance of the study at hand can be divided into two parts: theoretical and practical. As for the former, it comprises clarifying the theoretical and scientific background of the importance and role of critical thinking skills in implementing learning objectives in the primary stage. Similarly, there is also the clarity and analysis of the teacher's role in equipping students with critical thinking skills, particularly in the primary stage. The last of the points related to

the theoretical significance, is the clarification of problems and obstacles faced by the teacher, as well as the teaching performance in developing critical thinking skills for primary school students.

In regard to the practical significance, the study presents applied results that demonstrate the impact and importance of primary school teachers' adoption of strategies that develop critical thinking skills. In addition to this, the teacher's competencies related to her ability to develop critical thinking skills for students in the primary stage were shown. The third point of significance is that the study sheds light on teaching strategies and models that help the teacher develop critical thinking skills for primary school students.

Definition of Terms

Critical Thinking:

A purposeful mental activity is based on cognitive skills related to reasoning, which in turn leads to good results in interpretation, subjecting information and data to the process of sorting and analyzing, realizing the facts in the information in an objective manner, and making distinguished judgments based on this information. Critical thinker is able to distinguish problems and accept generalizations if there is evidence or proof. This is in addition to being proficient in applying those trends (Aripin et al., 2020).

In this study, critical thinking is defined as a mental activity that depends on cognitive aspects in which the primary school student can analyze and interpret situations, information, and events, and can infer and extrapolate, and thus reach decision-making capabilities or creatively solve a problem.

Critical Thinking Skills:

(Swartz et al., 1999) classified thinking skills into three categories, namely; idea generation skills, skills related to creative thinking, and skills to clarify ideas, which is also called critical thinking.

1 -The skill of analysis indeed determines the relationships with intended and actual connotations between phrases, questions, concepts, adjectives, other, formulas to express a belief, judgment, experience, information, or opinion skills, including sub-skills.

2 -The skill of induction means that the validity of the results is related to the validity of the premises. The induction includes the indications and judgments that a person issues after referring to a situation or events.

3 -The skill of inference is intended to allow for practice of a set of operations that depend on generating arguments and assumptions, searching for evidence, arriving at results, and identifying correlations and causal relationships.

4 -The skill of inference refers to identifying and providing the necessary elements to extract logical conclusions from the intended or actual inferential relationships from among phrases, adjectives, or any form of expression (Mulalić, 2022)

These are the skills (interpretation, analysis, induction, inference, inference, problem problem-solving, and decision-making) that the primary school student acquires while dealing with the information and knowledge he/she encounters. The teacher plays a distinguished role by employing teaching strategies in their development.

Primary School Stage

This is the educational stage that starts from the first grade and extends to the end of the sixth grade, between the ages of (6-12) years, in which the students' levels of knowledge and skills are developed (Herlina & Syahfitri, 2022).

Delimitations of the Study:

Subject: Critical thinking skills for primary education teacher's perspectives

Location: Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

Participants: Female primary school teachers

Time: During the academic year 2021/2022

Review of Literature

A study by (Al-Deeb, 2022) aimed to identify the effectiveness of a unit developed according to the SWOM strategy-which is concerned with the application of a set of organized, hierarchical questions and ideas. It helps the learner understand and control his/her cognitive performance and thus develops the thinking skills by promoting the skills of mathematical prowess and critical thinking among the sixth students. The sample was divided into two experimental groups of 24 students, and the study concluded that the unit of geometry and measurement developed according to the SWOM strategy has a significant impact on the experimental group students in all critical thinking skills.

A study by (Basal, 2020) aimed to identify the role of primary school teachers in developing critical thinking skills among students. To achieve the study's goal, the descriptive analytical approach was applied by distributing a questionnaire to a sample of 108 teachers in Gaza. A percentage of 80.34% was determined which meant that there are no statistically significant differences regarding the average estimates of the basic stage teachers for their role in developing critical thinking skills among the students at this stage due to the variables of gender, experience, and specialization.

Another study by (Al-Naif, 2018) aimed to identify the effectiveness of a program based on action research in developing critical thinking skills for eighth grade learners. To achieve the goal of the study, the experimental method was applied on a sample of 35 male and female students, and the number of the experimental group

comprised 17 male and female participants. The California Critical Thinking Test was conducted before/after on five skills. That included analysis, conclusion, inference, and evaluation, in addition to the training program that was built based on procedural research. The teacher's viewpoints through the action research strategy have an impact on preparing for a training program that has an influence on developing critical thinking among basic stage students.

A study by (Nasour& Abu Shaheen, 2020) aimed to analyze the content of the social studies curriculum in the light of critical thinking skills by applying it to the fifth grade of primary school. To achieve the goal of the study, the researcher used the descriptive approach to prepare a list of basic and secondary critical thinking skills. The main skills included interpretation, evaluation of arguments, defining assumptions, and the skill of inference and reasoning. The most available sub-skills were setting criteria for field study.

Previous studies have emphasized the importance of critical thinking skills and considered higher-order thinking skills that help develop creative thinking. Similarly, these are an essential step in students' acquisition of the life skills necessary for twenty-first-century skills. Preparing the theoretical background as a whole, there is great agreement on the impact of critical thinking skills their impact on the extent to which the teacher adopts appropriate methods and strategies in teaching them. Therefore, this study aimed to identify the point of view of primary school teachers about the importance of students acquiring those skills, the importance of including them in the curriculum, the level of support for the teacher and the adoption of getting a role in developing those skills among students, especially at the primary education stage.

Theoretical Framework:

With the intent to contribute towards building on advanced knowledge and given the urgent need for advanced educational technologies, researchers and educators directed their efforts toward the development sector in students, especially critical thinking skills to meet new challenges and give students the ability to deal with reality with its new variables and thus helping to make sound decisions related to acquiring and employing knowledge (Herlina&Syahfitri, 2022).

Critical thinking is one of the most important skills that students need in life and educational situations, and it needs continuous development. Delva Group (Experiences of Critical Thinking) believes that the concept of criticism means that the individual has an open and flexible mind and is able to judge things in addition to his/her ability to summarize and analyze as it transforms. In other words, this is the process of acquiring knowledge from a passive receiving state to a mental activity that focuses on mastering knowledge and improving academic abilities. Likewise, it also includes providing the opportunity to practice different styles of thinking and the ability to provide more accurate interpretations and thus make appropriate decisions and free thought to objectivity and impartiality (Noni & Abdullah, 2018).

Hence, the importance of shifting to education is based on employing critical thinking skills that instill and develop the ability to deal with knowledge efficiently. Furthermore, it requires acquiring capabilities in analysis, interpretation, evaluation, and conclusion. This allows for adopting sound beliefs and the ability to distinguish between facts, and opinions, as well as evaluate simple and complex cognitive claims without jumping to conclusions. This way, learners are able to draw conclusions in a sound logical manner, taking into account the avoidance of subjective factors that affect proper comprehension.

The quality of education has become a primary objective of educational policies in an attempt to gain the necessary control needed to achieve the educational outcomes that meet the standards set. Education at the basic stage is a wide field for the contributions of educational innovation through the role of the teacher in developing students' skills as a link between the educational curriculum and achieving its goals. Teaching and evaluation strategies are a response to the requirements of the educational system and education reform to achieve the competencies of creative thinking and for students to have the ability to solve problems in the future (Nurita&Ramadhani, 2022). (Zulmaulida et al., 2018) indicated that children are creative and rely on imagination, which is the basis of creativity and is infested in all aspects of life. This is what modern education seeks, as thinking is a skill and can be developed to bring the learner to creativity.

From the foregoing, we find that optimal learning can only be initiated by creating and forming the learner's motives and ability to participate positively in the learning process (Reid et al., 2014), as well as achieving success in various educational situations by directing learning activities to meet the educational goals of skill development. Based on the importance of thinking skills, criticism was of great importance in adopting teaching strategies that enhance those skills since the basic education stages seek to enhance students' abilities to adapt, integrate and achieve effective learning. Advanced independent education provides an opportunity for the learner to develop his/her skills through interaction with educational situations.

Given the importance of the above, it is possible to build on the theories that support the basis of constructing knowledge, the most important of which is the constructivist theory, which is concerned with building and forming knowledge by paying attention to how knowledge is acquired, organized and stored in the learner's memory and how to use it to achieve more learning and thinking capabilities. Among the models that were derived from the constructivist theory is the constructivist learning model, which has a clear impact on teaching basic stage basis age develop achievement and thinking skills (Erşan&Er, 2021).

Critical Thinking Skills:

There is a difference in views between curriculum experiences and teaching methods with rebooting critical thinking skills, but according to the objectives of the study, the researcher will adopt the Watson and Glaser classification, which included interpretation, deduction, understanding assumptions, and evaluating arguments and proofs (Firmansyah&Suhandi, 2021). These are as follows:

Interpretation Skill:

This skill refers to the learner's ability to identify the idea, recognize logical explanations, and decide whether those generalizations or results based on certain information are acceptable. It also measures the student's skill in judging evidence and proofs (Haq&Sawitri, 2021).

Deduction Skill:

This skill refers to the learner's ability to derive a particular conclusion from certain facts that have been observed or assumed from given facts. The conclusion leads to distinguishing between different degrees of right and wrong in the light of the given information and through which certain conclusions are reached according to the information obtained (Jean & Keejar, 2016).

Recognition of Assumptions skill:

This means the student's ability to distinguish between the degree of truthfulness of specific information and the distinction between opinion, truth, and the purpose of the given information.

Evaluation of Arguments skill:

This skill refers to the student's ability to evaluate, accept or reject the proposed idea or ideas and to distinguish between strong arguments related to an issue or weak arguments that are not related to the topic or issue.

Components of Critical Thinking:

Critical thinking consists of several components, including the following:

1. Knowledge:

The cognitive domain for the critical thinker is a field of practice, and then knowing the sources of information belonging to the topic or issue is content and an essential component of critical thinking. In the implementation of the skill, there is a set of criteria that help define a specific skill, and a set of rules that represent broad lines that guide the implementation of the skill (Hairunnisaet al., 2022).

2. Skills:

Critical thinking depends on a set of other skills, which include mental skills, observation skills, discrimination skills, comparison, interpretation and analysis, all of which help the thinker in formulating, organizing, and evaluating information.

3. Trends and Values:

Critical thinking depends on elements of values, emotions, and personal judgments, as well as skills in perseverance and accuracy because it is difficult to separate objectivity and personality in any work that targets knowledge (Sudirman&Yusnaeni, 2020).

Requirements for Developing Critical Thinking Skills

The development of critical thinking requires the collaboration of those in charge of the educational process to bear the responsibility of training students to think critically. This also requires curriculum developers, supervisors, or teachers, to make the necessary decisions to include skills in school subjects, as well as design activities and exercises, and work on developing educational objectives and various assessment tools.

The role of the supervisors is to encourage the teacher to develop critical thinking through planning and implementation of the educational process. Here, the teacher has the main role in developing critical thinking, as it is one of the most important factors for success. It helps students to research and investigate away from indoctrination and use modern methods and strategies that develop thinking skills. The role of the teacher is represented in his/her ability to design educational situations that prepare students that have a proper order to train in gaining. Students will not be able to develop their thinking for the better only by participating in activities that help them to do so. Rather, the chosen activities should encourage them to communicate effectively and create dialogue by asking questions that develop higher-order thinking skills. This is in addition to the importance of employing drawings and mind maps to help students derive relationships between concepts and ideas, and thus have an impact on developing students' thinking skills (Hasanpouret al., 2015).

The researchers identified five requirements for developing critical thinking skills, and these five requirements cannot be excluded for the development of critical thinking skills. They include:

1) Knowledge Base:

By it, the researcher means the student's previous and acquired level of knowledge, which is necessary to sense the contradiction or space in which critical thinking is built.

2) Events and Situations:

By this, the researcher means learning situations designed by the teacher that elicit a sense of contradiction and the need to think, analyze, explain and debate between arguments, evidence, and proofs.

3) Personal View:

By it, the researcher means the personal characteristics of the student according to his/her knowledge which made the students show a personal trait that he employs in trying to explain situations and events and thus create a feeling of contradiction or otherwise.

4) Feeling of Contradiction:

By it, the researcher means the student's feeling of thinking motives as a result of feeling different or divergent, or of possibilities for viewpoints when building on knowledge, and the steps of critical thinking follow.

5) Solve the contradiction:

Meaning the student's ability to include the constituent aspects of critical thinking and seek to resolve the contradiction through multiple steps, which is the basic structure of critical thinking (Hasanpour, 2015).

Critical Thinking Criteria:

It means the general specifications agreed upon by researchers in the field of thinking. These criteria represent guidelines for both the teacher and the student who must adhere to them in the process of thinking in general and critical thinking in particular, the most prominent of which are:

a) Clarity in the sense of formulating ideas and information in a clear and understandable manner. This means moving away from superficiality in dealing with topics with a high degree of depth in thinking.

c) Breadth: meaning familiarity with all aspects of the subject of thinking in a broad and holistic manner.

d) Logic in the broadly and holistically sequential and coherent manner that leads to the view that the idea or information is correct and reliable from the source through evidence and proofs.

h) Accuracy: It is intended to give the subject of the proofs due treatment and effort to make the fewest possible errors.

g) Connectivity in the sense of determining the relationship and the extent of interdependence between the elements of the subject of thinking (Fadilla et al., 2021).

The Importance of Teaching Students Critical Thinking Skills:

The importance of teaching critical thinking skills can be identified in:

a) Transforming the process of acquiring knowledge from a state of passive reception to actively participating in a mental activity that leads to a deeper understanding of knowledge and thus higher and more quality educational outcomes.

b) Develop the student's ability to be independent in thinking and the ability to develop self-learning skills and development and participate in creating creativity.

c) Encouraging sound thinking organized by lessons based on employing appropriate logical criteria to judge information and understand the nature of knowledge, situations and events.

d) Increasing the learner's confidence in his/her abilities and raising the level of self-esteem when facing life's problems and seeking to confront and overcome them and make decisions regarding them.

c) The practice of reasoning and avoiding errors and incorrect ideas helps to realize contradictions and to pay attention to fallacies and to exclude them rather than building on them.

h) Providing the learner with the opportunity to achieve self-learning and creating opportunities for growth, development, creativity and serious research.

g) Understanding different points of view and how to communicate with different ideas and cultures.

D) Creating a system for students that enables them to have the motivation to learn and achieve, contribute to the development of society and participate in the transition towards a knowledge economy (Cotter, 2022)(Erito et al., 2021).

Methodology:

Study Approach:

To achieve the aim of the study, descriptive and analytical approaches will be used. "The descriptive approach is the approach of selecting data and facts, and then classifying them, in addition to careful in-depth analysis to arrive at generalizations about the subject of the study." (Saber & Khafaja, 2002, p.87)

Sample and Sampling:

The study's population was limited to obtaining female teachers' perceptions of critical thinking skills for primary education. A total of 385 female teachers who taught in the public primary schools affiliated to the Diriyah office in the region of Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, during the academic year 2021, were invited to complete and return the survey. Eventually, 197 completed the survey and submitted their responses.

The frequencies and percentages of the sample were calculated according to the following:

1-Distribution of Study Sample Experience

Table (1) Distribution of Study Sample by Experience

Experience	Frequency	Percent
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Less than 5 years	69	35.0%
Between 6 and 10 years	75	38.1%
More than 10 years	53	26.9%
Total	197	100%

From **Table (1)**, the researcher concludes that (38.1%) of the study sample have from 6 to 10 years of experience, (35 %) of the study sample have 5 years of experience, and (26.9 %) of the study sample have more than 10 years of experience

2-Distribution of Study Sample by qualifications

Table (2) Distribution of Study Sample by qualifications

Qualification	Frequency	Percent
Bachelor's degree	112	56.9%
Diploma	62	31.4%
Master's/PhD degree	23	11.7%
Total	197	100%

As shown in Table (2), (56.9%) of the study sample stated that their **qualification** is a bachelor's degree, (31.4 %) of the sample obtained a diploma, and (11.7 %) have a master's/PhD degree.

Data Collection Instrument:

A questionnaire was designed by the researcher, which consisted of two axes, each axis included a number of items as follows:

The axes of the questionnaire

The first axis: The degree of knowledge of primary school teachers about critical thinking skills consisted of 20 items divided into 5 domains.

The second axis: The importance of including critical thinking skills in curriculum from the point of view of primary school teachers consisted of 5 items.

Participants were asked to rate the extent to which they agreed or disagreed with each statement with 5-point Likert scale

Reliability and Validity:

After the completion of the preparation of the study tools and the formulation of the statements, the initial tools were presented to a group of professors in order to ascertain the extent to which each statement was related to the factor to which it belongs. This was also done to check the clarity and integrity of the formulation of the statements until the study tool took its final form and consisted of (20) items.

With regards to the validity of the questionnaire used in this study, the researcher calculated internal consistency by determining the Pearson correlation coefficient between each item and the axis that belonged to the pilot sample study, which consisted of (30) teachers from outside the study sample, and had the same characteristics as the study sample. This is shown as follows:

Table (3) Pearson Correlation Coefficient between the Item and the Axis

The degree of knowledge of primary school teachers about critical thinking skills						The importance of including critical thinking skills in curriculum	
No	correlation coefficient	No	correlation coefficient	No	correlation coefficient	No	correlation coefficient
1	.667**	8	.607**	15	.704**	1	.605**
2	.599**	9	.592**	16	.582**	2	.559**
3	.586**	10	.672**	17	.647**	3	.596**
4	.618**	11	.727**	18	.722**	4	.703**
5	.504**	12	.742**	19	.582**	5	.663**
6	.151**	13	.679**	20	.647**		
7	.611**	14	.731**				

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results in **Table (3)** show that all Pearson correlation coefficients between each item and the related axis, come with a high degree of significance (0.01), which indicates a high degree of internal consistency validity of the terms of the questionnaire axes.

To ensure of the reliability of the questionnaire used in this study, the researcher used Cronbach's Alpha test to the pilot sample study which consisted of (30) teachers from outside the study sample and had the same characteristics as the study sample as shown in the following table

Table (4) Cronbach's Alpha Coefficients

Items	N	Cronbach's Alpha
The degree of knowledge of primary school teachers about critical thinking skills	20	.859
The importance of including critical thinking skills in curriculum	5	.837
Total degree	25	.855

The results in **Table (4)** show that the reliability coefficients value of the all items of the questionnaire were all of high scores approaching the correct one and the total reliability of the questionnaire was (0.855), which is a high value. Approaching the correct one refers to the reality of the questionnaire for the application and reliability of the results.

Study Procedures:

To answer the questions presented in the study, a myriad of approaches were taken, including the review and inclusion of all previous studies and research in the field, regardless of whether they were Arab or foreign. Upon the completion of the review, a questionnaire was identified and prepared as the study tool for the research. This questionnaire was then distributed to the participants during the academic year of 2021. Once gathered, the results were then monitored and analyzed.

Data Analysis

Depending on the nature of the research and the goals it seeks to achieve, the data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) program, and the results were extracted according to the following statistical methods:

1. Frequencies and percentages: to know the characteristics of the individuals of the research sample according to personal data.
2. Means and standard deviations: to calculate the means of the questionnaire statements
3. Pearson Correlation Coefficient: to calculate the internal consistency and reveal the relationship between the questionnaire dimensions.
4. Alpha Cronbach coefficient: to calculate the reliability of the questionnaire.
5. One-way ANOVA test was conducted
- 6-The response score was determined to give a score of (5) for the response strongly agree, (4) for the response in agreement, (3) for the response as neutral, (2) for the response not agreeing, and (1) for the response strongly reject and the degree of agreement was determined according to the mean value as follows:

Degree	1-1.79	1.8-2.59	2.6-3.39	3.4-4.19	4.20-5.0
Agreement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	strongly agree

Results and Discussion

Introduction:

The main objective of this research was to determine the degree of knowledge of primary school teachers about critical thinking skills.

The questionnaires were prepared to facilitate achieving the objectives of the study and answer the questions therein, which areas follows:

The first question: What is the degree of knowledge of primary school teachers about critical thinking skills?

To study the degree of knowledge of primary school teachers about critical thinking skills, the mean and standard deviation are calculated to the domains of the first axis as follows:

1- Conclusion Skill

Table(6) Mean and Standard Deviation to the Items of “Conclusion”

No	Item	Mean	standard deviation	Agreement	Rank
1	I can suggest titles for reading texts	4.02	.748	Agree	3
2	The ability to draw conclusions based on results	3.79	.754	Agree	4
3	Allow students to predict possible outcomes	4.09	.629	Agree	2
4	Ability to track and link ideas to predict outcomes	4.18	.673	Agree	1
Total degree		4.02	0.701	Agree	

The results in Table (6) show that the degree of knowledge of primary school teachers about 'conclusion skills' was highlighted by the selection of the (Agree) option, with a mean of (4.02) and a standard deviation of (0.701). This low value indicates homogeneity in the opinions of the study sample on the degree of knowledge of primary school teachers about 'conclusion skills'.

The standard deviations of the items are between (.754, .629) and these low values indicate homogeneity in the opinions of the study sample regarding these items.

Item number(4) was ranked first: (Ability to track and link ideas to predict outcomes), the mean was(4.18), with a standard deviation of (0.673) and a collective response of (Agree).

The item ranked in the last place was item number (2): (The ability to draw conclusions based on results), the mean was (3.79), a standard deviation of (0.745) and a collective response of (Agree). The rest of the items also had collective responses of (Agree).

2- Analysis Skill

Table(7) The Mean and Standard Deviations to the Items of “Analysis”

No	Item	Mean	standard deviation	Agreement	Rank
5	Distinguish between words that are opposite or similar in meaning	3.96	.610	Agree	2
6	Distinguish between facts and opinions contained in texts	4.12	.891	Agree	1
7	Identify the causes and behaviors of individuals and groups and their motives in a particular situation	3.81	.601	Agree	4
8	Understand the relationship between cause and effect in the reading	3.95	0.66	Agree	3
Total degree		3.96	0.69	Agree	

The results in **Table (7)** show that the degree of knowledge of primary school teachers about 'Analysis skills' was based on the participants' selection of the (Agree) option, with a mean of (3.96) and the standard deviation was (0.69). The low value indicates homogeneity in the opinions of the study sample on the degree of knowledge of primary school teachers about 'analysis skills'.

The standard deviation of the items is between (0.891, 0.601). These low values indicate homogeneity in the opinions of the study sample on these items.

Item number (6) was ranked first as shown in the table: (Distinguish between facts and opinions contained in texts), the mean was (4.12), a standard deviation of (0.891) and a collective response of (Agree).

The last placed item was item number (7): (Identify the causes and behaviors of individuals and groups and their motives in a particular situation), the mean was (3.81), with a standard deviation of (0.601) and a collective response of (Agree). Similarly, the rest of other items also had responses of (Agree).

3- Interpretation Skill

Table(8) mean and standard deviation to the items of “Interpretation”

No	Item	Mean	standard deviation	Agreement	Rank
9	The ability to interpret the meaning of the text being read	3.91	.426	Agree	3
10	The ability to explain the author's point of view	3.67	.761	Agree	4
11	The ability to interpret the information contained in the readable text	3.98	.635	Agree	2

12	The ability to interpret the results in the light of the analysis of the available information	3.99	.611	Agree	1
Total degree		3.89	0.61	Agree	

As shown in **Table (8)**, the degree of knowledge of primary school teachers about 'Interpretation skills' was shown through the participants' selection of the (Agree) response, where the mean was (3.89) and standard deviation was low (0.61), indicating homogeneity in the opinions of the study sample on the degree of knowledge of primary school teachers about 'interpretation skills.'

The standard deviation of the items is between (0.761 and 0.426). The low values indicate homogeneity opinions of the study sample on these items.

Item number (12) was ranked in first place: (The ability to interpret the results in the light of the analysis of the available information), had a mean of (3.99), a standard deviation of (0.611) and a collective response of (Agree).

Item number (10) was ranked last: (The ability to explain the author's point of view), the mean was (3.67), with a standard deviation of (0.761) and a response of (Agree), and the rest of items had responses of (Agree)

4- Induction Skill

Table(9) Mean and Standard Deviation to the items of "induction"

No	Item	Mean	standard deviation	Agreement	Rank
13	Making generalizations by connecting the relevant parts	4.00	.618	Agree	1
14	Recognize the relationships between cause and effect by inference	3.96	.630	Agree	3
15	The ability to identify sub-ideas available in the reading text	3.97	.609	Agree	2
16	Extracting the technical features that distinguish the text from others	3.93	0.704	Agree	4
Total degree		3.97	0.64	Agree	

The results in **Table (9)** show that the degree of knowledge of primary school teachers about induction skills was shown through the (Agree) responses. The mean was (3.97) and the standard deviation had a low value of (0.64), indicating homogeneity in the opinions of the study sample on the degree of knowledge of primary school teachers about induction skills

The standard deviation of the items is between (0.704 and 0.609). These low values, indicate homogeneity in the opinions of the study sample on these items.

Item number (13) was ranked first: (Making generalizations by connecting the relevant parts), the mean was (4.0), with a standard deviation of (0.618) and a response of (Agree).

Item number (16) was placed last in the ranking: (Extracting the technical features that distinguish the text from others), the mean was (3.93), with a standard deviation of (0.704) and a collective response of (Agree). The rest of the items also had responses of (Agree).

5- Evaluation Skill

Table(10) Mean and Standard Deviation to the Items of "Evaluation"

No	Item	Mean	standard deviation	Agreement	Rank
17	Expressing an opinion and judging the read text objectively	4.00	.418	Agree	1
18	The ability to evaluate the idea contained in the read in terms of acceptance or rejection	3.95	.625	Agree	2
19	Evaluate arguments, opinions, and evidence in light of appropriate evidence	3.83	.699	Agree	3
20	Judging the degree of adequacy of information in the reading	3.75	.521	Agree	4
Total degree		3.88	0.57	Agree	

From Table (10), the researcher concludes that the degree of knowledge of primary school teachers about evaluation skills was shown through the (Agree) responses. The mean was (3.88) with a standard deviation of

(0.57). The low value indicates homogeneity in the opinions of the study sample on the degree of knowledge of primary school teachers about evaluation skills.

The standard deviation of the items is between (0.699 and 0.418). These low values indicate homogeneity in the opinions of the study sample regarding these items.

Item number (17) was ranked first: (Expressing an opinion and judging the read text objectively), the mean was (4.0), with a standard deviation of (0.418) and a response of (Agree).

Item number (20) was last in the rankings: (Judging the degree of adequacy of information in the reading), the mean was (3.75), with a standard deviation of (0.521) and a response of (Agree). The rest of the items had responses of (Agree).

Table(11) Mean and Standard Deviation to the domains of First Axis

No	Domain	Mean	standard deviation	Agreement	Rank
1	Conclusion	4.02	0.701	Agree	1
2	Analysis	3.96	0.69	Agree	3
3	Interpretation	3.89	0.61	Agree	4
4	Induction	3.97	0.64	Agree	2
5	Evaluation	3.88	0.57	Agree	5
Total degree		3.94	0.64	Agree	

As shown in **Table (11)**, the degree of knowledge of primary school teachers about critical thinking skills was with the response of (Agree), the mean was (3.94) and the standard deviation was (0.64). This low value indicates homogeneity in the opinions of the study sample on the degree of knowledge of primary school teachers about critical thinking skills.

For the ‘Conclusion Skills’, the mean was (4.02), with a standard deviation of (0.701) and a collective response of (Agree).

‘Evaluation skills’ were placed last in the rankings, with a mean of (3.88), a standard deviation of (0.57), and a collective response of (Agree).

The first of the four questions was designed to reveal the participants’ level of knowledge about critical thinking skills. What emerged from the result analysis was proof that the participating teachers are knowledgeable in regard to critical thinking skills. Findings agree with the study conducted by Kamarulzaman et al. (2021) which revealed that primary school teachers understood the concept of critical thinking and believed that it is important to students. When teachers are able to exhibit their knowledge and mastery of these skills, it can be expected that their effectiveness in equipping students with critical skills is significantly enhanced. This is because the teacher’s own content knowledge has an impact on how they interpret content and ultimately affects their ability to support students in acquiring critical thinking skills. To this extent, these results assert that the participants are capable of guiding students in developing and refining skills which allow the learners to think more creatively, coherently, effectively and more importantly, critically. Previous studies in the field have gathered similarly results on content knowledge using surveys as the data collection tools, hence the questionnaire was also favored amongst other potential substitutes.

The second question: What is the importance of including critical thinking skills in curriculum from the point of view of primary school teachers?

To study the importance of including critical thinking skills in curriculum from the point of view of primary school teachers, the mean and standard deviations were calculated for the items of the second axis as follows:

Table(12) Mean and Standard Deviation to the Items of “Second Axis”

No	Item	Mean	standard deviation	Agreement	Rank
1	Critical thinking assists students in identifying strengths and weaknesses in their thinking in order to retain strengths and improve weaknesses.	4.19	.601	Agree	1
2	Critical thinking helps students to analyze and then evaluate and examine the ideas and information they receive.	3.65	.769	Agree	4
3	Critical thinking helps students to make fruitful decisions.	3.98	.647	Agree	2
4	Critical thinking develops the ability to understand and consider others’ points of view.	3.86	.514	Agree	3
5	Critical thinking improves the ability to balance their logic and emotion.	3.46	.974	Agree	5

Total degree	3.83	0.701	Agree
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The results in Table (12), show that the importance of including critical thinking skills in curriculum from the point of view of primary school teachers was with the response of (Agree). The mean was (3.83) and the standard deviation was (0.701). The low value indicates homogeneity in the opinions of the study sample on the importance of including critical thinking skills in curriculum from the point of view of primary school teachers. The standard deviation of the items is between (0.974 and 0.514). These low values indicate homogeneity in the opinions of the study sample regarding these items.

With regards to item number (1): (Critical thinking assists students in identifying strengths and weaknesses in their thinking in order to retain strengths and improve weaknesses.), the mean was (4.19), with a standard deviation of (0.601) and a collective response of (Agree).

Item number (5) was placed last in the rankings: (Critical thinking improves the ability to balance their logic and emotion.), the mean was (3.46), with a standard deviation of (0.974) and a collective response of (Agree). Likewise, the rest of the items also had responses of (Agree).

Data from a survey distributed to the participants supported the notion that the primary school teachers hold the view that critical thinking skills are paramount to a curriculum and should therefore be included. These results are supported by those in a study by Nasour and Abu Shaheen (2020) as they are both in agreement. If we were to consider the concept that 'teacher perceptions affect their practice' to be true, which is what many people argue, then it can be deduced that the participating teachers would give great value to equipping students with these skills. In other words, the high merit that the teachers have for the inclusion of critical thinking skills signals an innate desire to effectively teach students these skills as part of a curriculum. The perceptions of the participants also demonstrate a wholly new ideology, which is that if critical thinking skills were embedded in curricula, students can take charge of their own learning and thus expand perspectives and become masters at navigating decisions. The views of the teachers here also show a paradigm shift, which is that professional practitioners in education no longer hold the view that content knowledge is enough for learners to achieve success. Rather, students need to be critical thinkers, a goal which can only be realized if the skills being discussed, are an aspect of the curriculum.

The third question: Are there statistically significant differences in the viewpoint of primary school teachers towards students' acquisition of critical thinking skills due to the variable of qualifications?

To answer this question, the researcher used (one-way Anova test) and the results are shown as follows:

Table(13) Differences in the viewpoint of primary school teachers towards students' acquisition of critical thinking skills due to the variable of qualifications

	Sum squares	Df	Mean squares	F	Sig
Between groups	.259	2	.086	.510	.677
Within groups	9.475	194	.169		
Total	9.734	196			

From **Table (13)**, the researcher concludes that there are no statistically significant differences in the viewpoint of primary school teachers towards students' acquisition of critical thinking skills due to the variable of qualifications where the significant value (0.677) was more than (0.05).

The perceptions of the participants were not affected by the variable of qualifications. These results are supported by the findings in a study conducted by Basal (2020), which sought to answer the same question in a similar setting. The results were obtained from participants who had different qualifications, which show the full spectrum of expertise documents accepted or required to be a primary school teacher. Additionally, this fortifies the results the second question of this study as it highlights that the participants have strong belief in the efficacy of critical thinking skills.

The fourth question: Are there statistically significant differences in the viewpoint of primary school teachers towards students' acquisition of critical thinking skills due to the variable of experience?

To answer this question, the researcher used (one-way Anova test) and the results are shown as follows:

Table(14) Differences in the viewpoint of primary school teachers towards students' acquisition of critical thinking skills due to the variable of experience

	Sum of squares	Df	Mean squares	F	Sig
Between groups	.404	2	.202	1.235	.118
Within groups	9.329	194	.164		
Total	9.734	196			

As shown in Table (14), there are no statistically significant differences in the viewpoint of primary school teachers towards students' acquisition of critical thinking skills due to the variable of experience where the significant value (0.118) was more than (0.05).

Results from the study's last question revealed that the variable of experience did not have an impact on the

participants' perceptions regarding their learners' acquisition of critical thinking skills. The results for this particular question are also in agreement with what Basal (2020) concluded in his study.

Conclusion:

In summary, the findings of the study at hand show that the participating teachers are not only aware of critical thinking skills, but they are well knowledgeable and hold them in high merit. The results also assert that for the participants, it is an innate belief that possession of knowledge is not enough, factors such as creativity, constructing, and critical thinking are just as vital. Furthermore, the views were not affected by the variables of experience and qualifications.

The study found that there were no statistically significant differences in the viewpoint of primary school teachers towards students' acquisition of critical thinking skills due to the variable of 'qualifications.' Similarly, this is also the case for the variable of 'experience'. From the findings of the study, it was also noted that teachers agreed that the criterion for critical thinking is to express ideas transparently, environmental related, and the data and arguments presented do not contradict each other. Likewise, the participants agreed that the characteristics of a critical thinking model comprise understanding the connections between ideas, thinking about assumptions, beliefs, and values, and having a consistent and systematic approach to problems. It was also agreed upon that examples of critical thinking include checking the credibility of the source, referrals to the opinions of specialists, and developing logical conclusions and solutions and testing them against relevant criteria. Lastly, synthesis, analysis, and understanding, are all encompassed within the stages of critical thinking, and this was also agreed upon by the participating teachers.

Finally, the findings of this study open up new avenues for further investigation and research. It will be important for future research to look at how male teachers perceive critical thinking to determine the similarities and differences between male and female teacher perceptions toward critical thinking.

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